

TERMS RELATED TO CHILDREN'S DISEASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Murtazaeva Khadicha Nuriddinovna

English teacher at Termez branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7981752>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21th May 2023

Accepted: 28th May 2023

Online: 29th May 2023

KEY WORDS

English, medicine, higher education, modular system of education, professional development of medical students.

ABSTRACT

The modern world needs competent and mobile medical professionals who are able to work in a multicultural society anywhere in the world. The purpose of this work is to determine the structure and content of the discipline "Foreign Language", which would contribute to a more conscious, active and motivated assimilation of the subject. The research methodology was federal state educational standards, programs of the discipline "Foreign language" for higher educational institutions and the existing literature on the research problem. To determine specific situations for the further use of a foreign (English) language, a focus group survey was conducted. The result of the study is the definition and justification of the structure of the course "Foreign language" with the proposed topics and grammatical material, divided into modules. The authors of the study propose a course model consisting of three consecutive modules based on the needs of the trainees and the thematic content of the discipline. The proposed model of the course for teaching a foreign language will allow you to quickly form the universal competencies necessary for the future doctor and integrate into the professional community without any problems.

Introduction: Modern society is in a state of constant change due to a number of factors, such as globalization, migration, informatization and digitalization, increased competition in the economy [Avota, 2018], and, finally, the Covid-19 pandemic. The latter has become a real test for all countries and industries, including the education system. The changed situation entails adaptation, modification and selection of approaches, methods and teaching aids, while the content of the discipline does not change, but remains fixed in accordance with the federal state educational standards of higher education, basic professional educational programs, curricula and work programs.

The question arises - how to transform the discipline "Foreign Language", so that in modern conditions and taking into account world trends, graduates of medical areas of training can successfully integrate into a multicultural society? Thus, the purpose of this study is to determine the structure and content of the course "Foreign Language" in higher medical schools so that they correspond to the challenges of the current situation. Achieving this goal involves solving several problems: a) to study the current federal state educational standards of higher education; b) to analyze Russian and foreign approaches to the development of the content of the discipline "Foreign Language", c) to develop the structure and thematic planning of the course "Foreign Language" in higher educational institutions of the medical profile, taking into account the needs of students.

English is chosen as the basis, which is considered the international language of communication, the so-called lingua franca, since knowledge of English contributes to further academic and professional development, international communication, and scientific research [Stebletsova et al., 2015; Abugohar et al., 2019; Džuganová, 2019; Lodhi et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2019]. The system of Russian higher education is determined by the Federal State Educational Standards for Higher Education (FSES HE). In accordance with the Federal State Educational Standard, a graduate of a higher educational institution must have a number of competencies in relation to English or another foreign language. Four most popular training programs at a medical university were selected for analysis: General Medicine, Dentistry, Pediatrics, and Pharmacy. Thus, future pharmacists should form a universal communicative competence, that is, be able to introduce modern communication technologies in foreign languages into educational and professional interaction.

In addition, a graduate of this area of study should be able to apply modern communication technologies, including in a foreign language, for academic and professional interaction and be able to analyze and take into account the diversity of cultures in the process of intercultural interaction:

1. As for the programs "General Medicine", "Dentistry", and "Pediatrics", new federal standards are currently presented for discussion
2. According to these documents, students should be able to carry out business communication in oral and written forms in the state language of the Russian Federation and a foreign language, be able to perceive the intercultural diversity of society in the socio-historical, ethical and philosophical contexts, manage their time, build and implement a self-development trajectory on based on the principles of lifelong learning. Federal state educational standards are reflected in the work programs of academic disciplines.

At the Northern State Medical University (SSMU, Arkhangelsk), students of the areas of study "General Medicine", "Dentistry" and "Pediatrics" study the discipline "Foreign Language" in the first semester of the first year. The purpose of the discipline is to master the basics of oral and written forms of communication necessary for professional development, and their use as a means of communication. In the second semester, future doctors and pediatricians study the Fundamentals of Professional Activity in a foreign language. This discipline is aimed at the formation of vocabulary and the development of professional skills and self-development.

As for future dentists, they are offered an elective course "Scientific and technical translation", related to the translation of medical texts to master the skills of understanding written sources. Pharmacy students study the discipline "Foreign Language" for three semesters, striving to master oral and written forms of communication in order to use them as a means of communication and self-development. The question often arises - why the level of a foreign language of graduates of higher educational institutions is not high enough? There may be several answers. So, according to S.P. Sinyavskaya, one of the reasons is "lack of continuity in teaching foreign languages at school and university" [Sinyavskaya, 2019, p. 28].

The researcher says that in a foreign language class, the teacher has to repeat a certain amount of knowledge that first-year students did not master at school [Sinyavskaya, 2019]. The second reason the researcher considers is the insufficient number of hours devoted to the study of a professional foreign language. Another reason for D.S. Mamonkina [Mamonkina, 2019] considers the fact that, while studying in the first and second years, students are not fully aware of the need and possibilities of a foreign language in their subsequent professional activities. The study of English during this period is associated to a greater extent with the implementation of the curriculum.

This idea is supplemented by a number of scientists [Suleimanova et al., 2016; Miskhodzheva, 2018], who argue that in the first and second years students master highly professional vocabulary in English, not knowing it in Russian, which can lead either to an incorrect understanding of the lexical unit, or to forgetting it in the future. The researchers suggest continuing the development of a narrowly focused vocabulary and professional topics in senior courses or in parallel with the study of major disciplines.

In many parts of the world, English for Medical Purposes is taught from the point of view of real situations, which means that the teaching of English is focused on a certain context and specific vocabulary. But, more importantly, teaching medical English is based on the development of communication skills, the ability to solve problems and make decisions [Milosavljevic et al., 2015]. At the end of the course, students should be able to understand professionally oriented texts about the latest developments in their field, practice and improve their oral and written skills, write scientific articles, participate in exchange programs and international scientific events. In other words, students must master functional language (standard phrases for communicating with patients, counseling, writing emails, etc.), language skills and systems [Antić, 2015].

The aims and outcomes of the various English language courses for medical students are generally the same. Only lexical content is subject to variations depending on specific professional areas, since each area (cardiology, dentistry, surgery, and others) has its own specifics. Thus, in Japan, dental students [Rodis, et al., 2014] after completing the course are able to: a) produce and perceive basic dental phrases, understand the speech of their patients, ask their patients about their medical and dental characteristics, explain some dental procedures, access and comprehend information for native speakers published on the Internet, for example, when searching for and submitting applications to international dental conferences or journals (after the basic course), and b) understand and respond to technical dental phrases, create and speak oral presentations on specific dental topics, communicate

with healthcare professionals through a variety of means (after completing the advanced course).

In Finland [Wallinheimo, Pitkänen, 2016], the focus is on interaction, as the future profession involves communication and context-specific activities. The course itself is based on task-based language learning, since learning is most effective when it is integrated with authentic tasks that are borrowed from everyday contexts. All materials are duplicated on the electronic learning platform Moodle. Typically, the lesson includes a preliminary stage (reading materials, watching videos, preparing presentations, drafting written assignments), classroom work (solving the task, report and discussion, analysis and evaluation, use of text, video and audio materials, feedback, writing summary, reviews, etc.), as well as the post-classroom stage (participation in discussions on the forum and chats, self-reflection, consultations with the teacher).

Researcher F.A. Miskhodzheva [Miskhodzheva, 2018], to expand the professional vocabulary, suggests working out industry vocabulary, pronunciation of English terms, and conducting a comparative analysis of terminological units and expressions in Russian and English. In the second module, special attention should be paid to the selection of texts for reading. They should contain information about the latest achievements in the field of medicine, correspond to the research interests of the trainees and serve as an additional source of professional knowledge.

The method of working with reading professional literature and academic writing can be as follows [Mungra, 2010]:

- a) read a clinical case, analyzing vocabulary and register,
- b) formulate questions to the patient in order to obtain clinically relevant information, formulate possible treatment options and make query in a medical database,
- c) find scientific publications relevant to a clinical case in databases and online libraries,
- d) analyze publications in order to determine the logic of the author and the structure of IMRaD, e) extract and structure characteristics from various scientific publications,
- f) evaluate the text of the article according to such linguistic features as academic register, syntax and semantics, interaction between the reader and the author, lexical and grammatical choice and others,
- g) read a scientific article in which the "Methods" section has been deleted, try to reconstruct this section based part of the article, and write the missing section.

Teaching a foreign language is usually not limited to the classroom and continues outside the classroom. Researchers note the productive use of such forms as student societies or circles, student scientific and practical conferences of various levels, subject Olympiads [Stebletsova, Rogozhina, 2015].

The modern development of technologies allows remote participation in various international conferences, competitions and improve skills at seminars. In addition, students with a good knowledge of the language can participate in exchange programs and have the opportunity to do internships or internships at foreign universities or medical institutions [Belova et al., 2018]. In conclusion, we note that the proposed modular training course for medical students, distributed over three years, will allow developing and enhancing

professional and academic skills and abilities and forming the necessary universal competencies.

Upon completion of the course, students will be able to understand and apply medical terminology, discuss and present professional information, read, understand and produce medical texts of various kinds, as well as be aware of the responsibility for learning and project the trajectory of their further development. The acquired skills will allow them to be more confident in situations related to communication in the academic and professional fields, achieve great success in their careers and become a sought-after specialist not only in Russia, but also at the international level.

It seems that the model of the course "Foreign Language" created by the authors can also be used as the basis for a similar modular course for students of other non-philological areas of study.

References:

1. Belova Yu. K. English as a tool for the professional development of a medical student / Yu. K. Belova, M. A. Medvedeva, O. V. Peshikov // Bulletin of the Council of Young Scientists and Specialists of the Chelyabinsk Region. 2018. No. 4 (23). pp. 13-16.
2. Gamanko R. A. The use of the project method in the formation of professional competencies of a medical student at foreign language lessons // Management of innovations: theory, methodology, practice. 2016. No. 17. P. 93-100.
3. Gizyatova L. A. Vocational-oriented teaching of English to medical students / L. A. Gizyatova, N. F. Plotnikova // Kazan linguistic journal. 2019. No. 2 (4). pp. 67-73.
4. Dubenkova L. V. English for medical purposes // Regional Bulletin. 2020. No. 10 (49). pp. 64-65.
5. Zabolotnova T. N. Motivation of medical students to learn a foreign language / T. N. Zabolotnova, A. Yu. Evstigneeva, L. A. Pavlova // Volga Pedagogical Search. 2013. No. 3 (5). pp. 77-82.
6. Krylov E. G. Bilingual education in engineering disciplines and a foreign language at the university. Moscow; Izhevsk: Institute for Computer Research. 2015. 148 p.
7. Mamonkina D.S. English language is the basis for the professional development of a doctor // Sustainable development of science and education. 2019. No. 1. S. 188-193.
8. Miskhodzheva F. A. Features of teaching a foreign (English) language for medical purposes in higher education // Bulletin of science and education. 2018. No. 10 (46). pp. 52-55.
9. Popova N.V., Kogan M.S., Vdovina E.K. Subject-Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) as a Methodology for Actualizing Interdisciplinary Relations in a Technical University // Bulletin of the Tambov University. Series Humanities. Tambov. 2018. V. 23. No. 173. S. 29-42.